

WAYS TO SOLVE PROBLEMS IN THE PREPARATION OF KURASH WRESTLERS

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Annotation: The article discusses the issues and problems of training kurash wrestlers, as well as ways to solve them. The juniors who are preparing to participate in responsible competitions for the national team in kurash wrestling were examined.

Key words: kurash wrestling, juniors, training, functional status.

Introduction: The use of various innovative methods that non-invasively show the whole catastrophic picture of metabolic disorders that occur during weight loss in juniors is useful not only for the young athletes themselves, but also for the entire coaching and teaching staff in the current system of training young wrestlers for a number of objective reasons [1, 2].

The task of maximum elimination of all unfavorable conditions associated with the implementation of activities aimed at reducing the body weight of an athlete in the pre-competitive period [4, 5, 6] is an urgent problem in elite sports and is the goal of this work.

Limiting attitudes are identified that reduce the motivation to take advanced training courses, including among coaches-teachers who educate a whole galaxy of young athletes, training or retraining, as well as develop an approach that increases the mood for learning, which was reflected in the assessment of criteria for developing a complex physical exercises and compiling a whole range of physical exercises aimed at general improvement and improvement of cognitive functions [3, 7, 8, 9].

Improving sports results in modern conditions of wrestling is becoming an increasingly difficult task, which is becoming more politicized, which is becoming even more relevant and significant [10, 11].

A detailed and clear analysis of the entire system of training young kurash wrestlers without embellishment and with the identification of all weaknesses is bold and relevant. All the mistakes in the training of young kurash wrestlers are analyzed, all the disadvantages of the training system for young wrestlers are shown, which is by no means critical, but serves only one purpose - to understand the weaknesses and identify ineffective approaches in the training system of young athletes and strengthen weaknesses, and even turn them into strong ones [12, 13].

The role of a coach-teacher is shown, playing the role of a sports strategist, psychologist, mentor, teacher, who knows how to build relationships with a single athlete who is in transitional adolescence, which is also complicated by hormonal changes in the body of a junior athlete, as well as having the skill to build intra-team relationships and sports strategies [14, 15, 16].

The application of innovative methods in elite sport has always been a relevant and interesting scientific approach to expanding the scope of competence of the entire coaching and teaching staff and an integrated scientific group. Therefore, the introduction of new research methods into the study of the functional and medico-biological component of elite sport is a relevant and progressive method [17, 18].

This paper outlines a clear plan for conducting a study regarding both monitoring the functional state of the body of athletes at the time of competitive activity, and after the competition, to track the rate of recovery mechanisms of the body of athletes from the stress of competitive activity.

Options for accelerating recovery phenomena in the body of athletes after competitions are proposed, using various methods as an example, which are compared with each other in terms of efficiency and effectiveness, which is accompanied by a detailed and clear analysis of the processes occurring under the

influence of the recovery methods used in the body of athletes during the entire observation period.

The problems of weight loss in athletes in the pre-competitive period were, are and will be, an actual problem, since the constant hormonal changes that accompany an athlete throughout his sports career become permanent causes of fluctuations in various adaptive processes, among which body weight is a kind of indicator of hormonal changes which, most of all, affects the body weight of young kurash wrestlers, due to age and psychological reasons.

The use of various innovative methods that non-invasively show the whole catastrophic picture of metabolic disorders that occur during weight loss in juniors is useful not only for the young athletes themselves, but also for the entire coaching staff in the current system of training young wrestlers for a number of objective reasons.

The hypothesis, which has always existed implicitly in the theoretical assumptions of a number of authors, that weight loss in the pre-competitive period is accompanied by a number of metabolic disorders, has been proved and shown by the authors in this practical work, which became possible thanks to innovative technologies for studying microcirculation and transcapillary metabolism at the microlevel.

The issues of theoretical substantiation of violations of metabolic processes occurring in the body of athletes in the pre-competitive period, which, as you know, are complicated not only by psychological stressful situations, but also by functional disorders of varying severity due to emergency functioning of the body, in the mode of pre-competitive training and weight loss, are covered.

Previous studies have shown that the use of weight loss techniques in athletes in the pre-competition period disrupts metabolic processes in the body. The use of restorative procedures to correct the identified violations is recommended. The theoretical base of violations occurring in the body of a junior athlete during weight loss is described, supported by practical results and own

developments, when working with juniors of the national team of the Republic of Uzbekistan in kurash wrestling.

Conclusions. This scientific and theoretical review highlights previously unraveled issues of the influence of the vegetative regulation of the body of a junior athlete and its violations on his training and competitive activities.

On the basis of independently conducted research and observations, the criteria affecting the quality of sports training of a young athlete were also identified. The factors of influence of pedagogical, psychological, medical, biological and social plans are clearly described and delineated, and in those contexts that are difficult to cover because of their implication.

It was possible to identify weaknesses that are justified both physiologically and pedagogically, knowing and exploring which it is possible to improve and bring to the forefront one of the best, traditionally, sports school for training Russian athletes, starting from their young age.

Correction of microcirculation disorders is an urgent problem that is known to all athletes and coaches who have at least once used the method of weight loss in the pre-competition period, the main difficulties of which are diet restriction, an increase in aerobic loads and a decrease in the amount of water drunk, which becomes a serious limiting factor for life .

The search for various recovery methods that would contribute to a more comfortable well-being of an athlete during this difficult period for him is an urgent task for any researcher conducting his research in the field of sports training. Hormonal and vegetative changes lay the functional basis for the formation of internal protective, adaptive mechanisms that provide adaptation.

References:

1. Турдимуродов, Д. (2023). Yuqori sinf o 'quvchilarida qat'iyatlilik sifatini jismoniy tarbiya darslarida tarbiyalash. *Ижтимоий-гуманитар фанларнинг долзарб муаммолари/Актуальные проблемы социально-гуманитарных наук/Actual Problems of Humanities and Social Sciences.*, 3(3), 218-223.

2. Турдимуродов, Д. Ю. (2022). Формирование у подростков волевых качеств в процессе физического воспитания. *Science and Education*, 3(7), 283-289.
3. Турдимуродов, Д. (2022). Жисмоний тарбия дарси мактаб ўқувчиларида иродавий сифатларни ривожлантирувчи восита сифатида. *Общество и инновации*, 3(6/S), 74-80.
4. Юлдошева, Ф. М. (2019). Психологические механизмы воздействия игры на младших школьников. *Вопросы педагогики*, (4-2), 240-243.
5. Юлдошева, Ф. М., & Избосарова, З. А. (2018). Особенности развития творческих способностей в дошкольном возрасте. *Вопросы педагогики*, (4-2), 117-118.
6. Юлдошева, Ф. М. (2020). Чувства и этические представления дошкольника. *Вопросы педагогики*, (5-1), 434-436.
7. Юлдошева, Ф. М. (2020). Взаимосвязь проблем воспитания познавательного интереса и развития мышления в процессе обучения математике. *Вопросы педагогики*, (6-1), 348-351.
8. Mamasaxatovna, Y. F. (2022). Maktabgacha ta'lim tarbiyachining innovasion faoliyatini shakllantirish shartlari. *Ta'lim va rivojlanish tahlili onlayn ilmiy jurnali*, 2(1), 134-137.
9. Mamasakhatovna, Y. F. (2022). Application of Interactive Board in Teaching Preschool Children. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 1(9), 79-83.
10. Mamasakhatovna, Y. F. *Modern Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*.
11. Tukhtayevich, T. P. (2022, October). Circle training in physical training of young kurash wrestlers. In *Proceedings of International Conference on Scientific Research in Natural and Social Sciences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 79-83).
12. Turdimurodov, D. Y. (2022, September). Formation of moral and volitional qualities of adolescents by means of physical education. In *International scientific conference "Innovative trends in science, practice and education"* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 198-204).

13. Turdimurodov, D. (2022). Volitional qualities of a person and their formation in adolescent age. *Models and methods in modern science*, 1(14), 13-17.
14. Yuldosheva Feruza Mamasaxatovna. (2022). Maktabgacha ta'limda steam ta'lim texnologiyasidan foydalanish zaruriyati. *Journal of new century innovations*, 2(1), 170–177.
15. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2023). Peculiarities of Volitional Qualities in Physical Education of Schoolchildren. *Web of Semantic: Universal Journal on Innovative Education*, 2(2), 217-220.
16. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2022). Education of moral-volitional and psychological qualities in athletes. *Problems and scientific solutions*, Australia, Melbourne.
17. Yuldashevich, T. D. (2022). Application of Innovative Technologies in the Process of Formation of Will Qualities. *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science*, 4, 826-828.
18. Yuldoshevich, T. D. (2021). The formation of readiness for skilled tensions in the process of physical education. In *Archive of Conferences* (Vol. 2124).